

The relationship of the quality of health services tangible dimensions with patient satisfaction in the health services of the Lepo-Lepo Health Center Kendari City, Indonesia

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Abstract

Currently, along with advances in the field of science and technology today, the understanding and needs of the community are also increasing in obtaining quality public services and satisfying customers. Public Health Center as health service providers need to synergize with these advances. The purpose of the study was to determine the relationship between the qualities of health services in the tangible dimension with patient satisfaction at the Lepo-Lepo Public Health Center, Kendari City in 2021. This type of research was a survey with a Cross Sectional Study approach. The study population was 448 patients. The research sample was 211 patients. Collecting data by using a questionnaire. Data analysis was performed by Univariate and Bivariate. The results showed that there was no correlation between tangibles and patient satisfaction in health services at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center, Kendari City in 2021 with a value of $p = 0.75$ ($p > 0.05$). Recommendation; Public Health Center should continue to improve professionalism in health services, increase the availability of service infrastructure and patient satisfaction.

Keywords: Public Health Center; Quality; Tangible; Satisfaction; Patient

1 Introduction

Article 5 of Law Number 36 of 2009 concerning Health mandates that safe, quality and affordable health services are the responsibility of the Government and the right of every person. Likewise, Article 42 paragraph 1 of Presidential Regulation Number 12 of 2013 concerning Health Insurance states that health services to Health Insurance participants must pay attention to service quality, be oriented to patient safety aspects, effectiveness of actions, suitability to patient needs, and cost efficiency. In the current era of the National Social Security System, especially in the health sector, the Public Health Center as the Technical Implementation Unit of the District/City Health Service is the front line in the implementation of basic health efforts, has the responsibility to provide health services for the community through the implementation of public health efforts and individual health efforts. These health efforts must be carried out in a comprehensive, tiered, integrated, quality, fair and equitable manner, as well as satisfying the entire community in the work area for which they are responsible [1].

The Public Health Center has responsibility for the work area, namely a sub-district. Public Health Center has a vision that is to achieve a healthy sub-district. Healthy sub-districts cover 4 main indicators, namely healthy relationships, healthy behavior, quality health service coverage, and population health status. To achieve this vision, Public Health Center need to be supported by quality health services [2].

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Health services are one of the sub-systems of national health services. Based on Minister of Health regulations number 75 of 2014 that must be carried out by Public Health Center is a service that is based on a national commitment to improve integrated public health status. Patient satisfaction is one of the important indicators in improving health services, because patients as bio-psychosocial beings require the fulfillment of expectations from health aspects (biological), satisfaction aspects (psychological), and cultural aspects. However, in the era of national health insurance, the quality of health services provided declined. This is caused by the lack of information provided by officers to the community, because it will affect the perception of patients who want to go to the Public Health Center [3].

Patient satisfaction is a manifestation of the patient's feelings and the level of feelings that arise as a feedback response from the health services they receive. Satisfaction will be achieved if the patient's expectations are met by the reality of the services they receive. There are 5 dimensions that represent the patient's perception of the quality of health services, namely; (1) reliability which measures the ability to provide services as promised accurately and reliably, (2) responsiveness, namely the ability to provide services as quickly as possible, (3) assurance associated with providing a sense of security and trust to patients, (4) empathy, namely the ability to give sincere personal attention to patients and (5) tangible where service providers are required to be able to display maximum resources in their services both in terms of equipment and service providers [2].

Problems with the quality of health services in Indonesia include the lack of evaluation of health services and satisfaction surveys that do not involve patients. Patient satisfaction is one of the important indicators in improving health services. The function of health services carried out by the government through organizations in the health sector with the main objective of maintaining and maintaining public health in a functional, proportional and professional manner [4].

According to [5] suggests that the concept of service quality related to patient satisfaction is determined by five elements commonly known as service quality "SERVQUAL" (reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy and tangible). The quality of health services shows the level of perfection of health services in creating a sense of satisfaction in each patient. The more perfect the satisfaction, the better the quality of health services.

Research results [2] show that patients are satisfied by comparing expectations and experiences that describe the level of patient satisfaction with health services in 5 dimensions of service quality. The overall level of satisfaction is categorized as Satisfied. The results of the study [6] stated that the overall satisfaction distribution was mostly in the satisfied category. Seen from each dimension, there is still a dissatisfied category on the assurance dimension, especially the item that the patient believes in the ability of the staff. In addition, there is no difference in satisfaction based on the characteristics of Gender, Age, and Occupation. However, there is a significant difference in satisfaction with the characteristics of education. The results of the study [7] said that there was a relationship between service quality (responsiveness, assurance, tangible, empathy and reliability) with patient satisfaction. The results of the study [8] said that there was a relationship between the quality of nurse care in the dimensions of reliability, responsiveness, assurance, attention and appearance with patient satisfaction at Balimbing Hospital. The results of the study [9] said that there was a relationship between Patient Satisfaction with Health Services (Responsiveness, assurance, tangible, empathy and reliability). The results of the study [10] said that there was a significant relationship between service quality and patient satisfaction. The results of the study [11] said that there was a significant relationship between service quality and patient satisfaction.

Based on an initial survey conducted at the Lepo-Lepo Public Health Center in Kendari City, several health care user patients obtained several service complaints including limited seating, lack of facilities, slow service of officers, sometimes long waiting times for doctors, and limited vehicle parking. Based on this information, researchers are interested in conducting research on health service satisfaction by patients at the Lepo-Lepo Public Health Center, Kendari City. The purpose of this study was to analyze the relationship between the qualities of health services in the tangible dimension with patient satisfaction at the Lepo-Lepo Public Health Center, Kendari City in 2021.

2 Material and methods

The type of research used is analytic survey research with a Cross Sectional Study approach. The size of the population of this study was 448 patients. The research sample obtained as many as 211 patients. Respondents' inclusion criteria were patients who visited at least 2 visits, resided in the working area of the Lepo-Lepo Health Center, and were willing to be respondents. Collecting data by using a questionnaire. Data analysis was carried out using Uni Variate and Bivariate.

3 Results

3.1 Univariate Analysis

3.1.1 Tangible

Tangible is the quality of service that is determined by looking at the physical appearance, equipment, appearance of employees, and existing means of communication [12]. The distribution of respondents according to Tangible is presented in table 1;

Table 1 Distribution of respondents according to tangibles in health services at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center, Kendari City in 2021

Number	Tangible	Amount (n)	Percentage (%)
1	Enough	171	81
2	Not Enough	40	19
Total		211	100

Source: Primary Data, year 2021

Table 1 shows that of the 211 respondents (100%), most of the respondents have sufficient tangibles, namely as many as 171 respondents (81%) compared to respondents who have less tangibles, namely as many as 40 respondents (19%)

3.1.2 Service Quality

According to [5] suggests that the concept of service quality related to patient satisfaction is determined by five elements commonly known as service quality "SERVQUAL" (reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy and tangible). The quality of health services shows the level of perfection of health services in creating a sense of satisfaction in each patient. The more perfect the satisfaction, the better the quality of health services. The distribution of respondents according to servqual is presented in table 2;

Table 2 Distribution of respondents according to Service Quality in health services at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center, Kendari City in 2021

Number	Service Quality	Amount (n)	Percentage (%)
1	Satisfied	152	72
2	Not satisfied	58	28
Total		211	100

Source: Primary Data, year 2021

Table 2 shows that of the 211 respondents (100%), most of the respondents have satisfied Service Quality, namely 152 respondents (72%) compared to respondents who have dissatisfied Service Quality, which is 58 respondents (28%).

3.2 Bivariate Analysis

3.2.1 Tangible Dimension

The relationship between tangibles and patient satisfaction in health services at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center in Kendari City can be presented in table 3.

Table 3. Shows that of the 171 respondents (100%) who have sufficient tangibles, there are more patients who state that they are satisfied with the Service Quality, as many as 124 respondents (72.5%) than patients who state that they are not satisfied with the Service Quality, which is 47 respondents. (27.5 %). Meanwhile, out of 40 respondents (100%) who have less tangibles, there are more patients who say they are satisfied with the Service Quality, as many as 28 respondents (70%) than patients who say they are not satisfied with the Service Quality, which is as many as 12 respondents (30%).

Table 3 The relationship between tangibles and patient satisfaction in health services at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center, Kendari City in 2021

Tangible	Service Quality				Amount (n)		P
	Satisfied		Not Satisfied		N	%	
	N	%	N	%			
Enough	124	72,5	47	27,5	171	100	0,750
Not Enough	28	70	12	30	40	100	
Total	152	72	59	28	211	100	

Source: Primary Data, year 2021

The results of the chi square test obtained a value of $p = 0.75$ ($p > 0.05$) which means that H_0 is accepted. This shows that there is no relationship between tangibles and patient satisfaction in health services at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center, Kendari City in 2021.

4 Discussion

The Relationship between Tangible Dimensions and Patient Satisfaction in Lepo-Lepo Health Center Health Services in 2021 Health Service Facility is a place used to organize health service efforts, whether promotive, preventive, curative or rehabilitative carried out by the local government and/or the community. Community Health Center, hereinafter referred to as Public Health Center, is a health service facility that organizes public health efforts and first-level individual health efforts, by prioritizing promotive and preventive efforts, to achieve the highest degree of public health in its working area. Health services are efforts provided by the Public Health Center to the community, including planning, implementation, evaluation, recording, reporting, and set forth in a system. Public Health Center have the task of implementing health policies to achieve health development goals in their working areas in order to support the realization of a healthy sub-district [13].

To support the achievement of health development, the government has provided several health facilities/facilities and their health workers. One of the health facilities that is widely used by the community is the Public Health Center. As the spearhead of health services and development in Indonesia, Public Health Center need to get attention, especially with regard to the quality of Public Health Center health services, so that in this case, Public Health Center especially those equipped with inpatient units are required to always improve the professionalism of their employees and improve their health facilities/facilities to provide satisfaction to the community who use health services.

Tangible is the quality of service that is determined by looking at the physical appearance, equipment, appearance of employees, and existing means of communication. Tangibles dimensions consist of: Cleanliness, tidiness and comfort of the room, Exterior and interior arrangement, Completeness, readiness and cleanliness of the tools used and Neatness and cleanliness of the appearance of officers [12].

Based on the research findings in table 1, it shows that, in general, patients who state that they are tangible are more numerous than patients who state that they are less tangible. This shows that the higher the tangible, the higher the level of patient satisfaction in health services. On the other hand, the lower the tangible, the lower the level of patient satisfaction with the health services of the Lepo-Lepo Public Health Center. This happens because patients are increasingly aware of their needs and desires in health services, where they want the quality of the services they receive in the form of the physical appearance of the Public Health Center, equipment, the appearance of officers, and existing communication facilities in accordance with the wishes and expectations of the patient. In the sense that a clean, neat, fragrant physical appearance will invite a sense of comfort and pleasing to the eye. The existence of cleanliness and tidiness of the equipment will give a sense of comfort and pleasure in the eyes of the patient. Likewise, good communication facilities and methods will make patients feel comfortable, so that services will have a positive impact on patient motivation in getting services.

Community demands for quality and quality health services are growing in line with the increasing level of knowledge and education and people's income. The development of the health sector must continue to be encouraged, so the implementation of services carried out by health service facilities by providing the best service for patients with the aim of creating patient satisfaction [14]

Patient satisfaction depends on the quality of health services. Measuring the level of patient satisfaction is closely related to the quality of service. Satisfaction occurs when the needs, desires, expectations of customers can be fulfilled. Patient satisfaction is a feeling of pleasure or satisfaction that the product or service received has met or exceeded his expectations. Patient satisfaction is one indicator of the quality of services we provide and patient satisfaction is a capital to get more patients and to get loyal patients. Loyal patients will reuse the same health services if the patient needs it again [14].

From the results of the study, it was found that in general, patients who stated that they were tangible were more than the number of patients who stated that they were less tangible. This happens because the patient wants the cleanliness of the room, the cleanliness of the equipment, the cleanliness of the staff's clothes, the cleanliness of the office yard, the neatness of the appearance of the officers, the neatness of the room, the neatness of the equipment, the comfort of the service room, the arrangement of interior and exterior properly, the completeness of equipment and medicines, and officer readiness.

Public Health Center is one of the health facilities that are widely used by the community. Public Health Center as the Technical Implementation Unit of the Health Service are the spearhead of health services in Indonesia [13]

Quality of service is one of the important factors in the utilization of health services. Assessment of the quality of good service is not limited to physical healing, but also to the attitudes, knowledge and skills of officers in providing services, communication, information, courtesy, punctuality, responsiveness. and the availability of adequate physical facilities and environment [15]

The results of the chi square test obtained a value of $p = 0.75$ ($p > 0.05$) which means that H_0 is accepted. This shows that there is no relationship between tangibles and patient satisfaction in health services at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center, Kendari City in 2021. The results of this study are not in line with the results of research [9] which says that there is a relationship between patient satisfaction with health services (responsiveness, assurance, tangible), empathy and reliability). Research [16] showed that the satisfaction level of outpatients with health services (Responsiveness, Assurance, Tangible, Empathy, and Reliability) was 99.47%. Almost all outpatients at the Mengwi I Health Center were satisfied with the health services they received there. Research [6] shows that the overall satisfaction distribution is mostly in the satisfied category. Research [17] found that the level of patient satisfaction with the tangible dimension is satisfied because it has a level of conformity above the overall average of service quality dimensions (79.70%). The level of patient satisfaction with the dimension of reliability (reliability) is less satisfied. The level of patient satisfaction with the responsiveness dimension is less satisfied. The level of patient satisfaction with the dimension of assurance (assurance) is less satisfied. The level of patient satisfaction with the dimensions of empathy (empathy) is satisfied. Research [18] found that tangibility and assurance have an effect on customer satisfaction of Sarila Husada Hospital Sragen patients.

From the statistical test results, it was found that there was no relationship between tangibles and patient satisfaction. In health services at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center, Kendari City in 2021, this happened because there were several factors that also influenced it in the form of the quality of service received by patients in the form of the physical appearance of the Public Health Center, equipment Public Health Center, the appearance of officers, and the existing communication facilities are not in accordance with the wishes and expectations of the patient. Patients want cleanliness of the room, cleanliness of equipment, cleanliness of staff's clothes, cleanliness of the office yard, neatness of the appearance of officers, neatness of the room, neatness of equipment, comfort of the service room, good interior and exterior arrangement, completeness of equipment and medicines, and readiness of officers.

This study is also not in line with the results of research [19], it was found that there was a significant relationship between Service Quality (Responsiveness, Assurance, Tangible, Empathy, and Reliability) with Patient Satisfaction in the medical records section of Muhammadiyah Hospital Bandung. Research [20] obtained the results of simultaneous analysis of the five variables both from physical evidence, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy affect patient satisfaction. Research [21] shows the results of the variables of physical evidence, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy have a positive influence on patient satisfaction using National Health Insurance at the Medical Rehabilitation Hospital. Research [22] showed that the quality of health services (Responsiveness, Assurance, Tangible, Empathy, and Reliability) with the level of patient satisfaction had a relationship.

5 Conclusion

There is no correlation between tangibles and patient satisfaction in health services at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center, Kendari City in 2021 with a value of $p = 0.75$ ($p > 0.05$). Suggestion; Public Health Center should continue to improve professionalism in health services, increase the availability of service infrastructure and patient satisfaction.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

All authors in the making of this scientific article have no conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

All informants/respondents involved in this study have stated their consent as informants/respondents to be interviewed and provided information/information in accordance with research needs.

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